

GENDER CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Kasimova Mashkhura Makhamadaliyevna

Tashkent University of Social Innovation

Teacher of the Department of “Pedagogy and Psychology”

e-mail: mashkhurakasimova5@gmail.com

Teachers believe that ideal students should possess the following qualities: first of all, they should be eager to learn, interested in learning, hardworking, good manners, and resilient. But if "When it comes to seeing how boys and girls graduate from school, boys, first of all, should be able to make decisions, confident in their abilities, purposeful, responsible for their work, have their own opinion, confident and courageous. They want to see girls as polite, able to get along with people, kind, feminine, gentle, modest, polite, proud, self-respecting, as well as girls who believe in their abilities and can make independent decisions.

So, when a child enters school, the teacher teaches them to be hardworking, intelligent, polite, capable of making decisions, self-confident, even courageous boys and girls who are capable of achieving what we need. Then they will become flexible and diligent, independent and self-confident people.

The relevance of the problem. This problem is very relevant today. The society in the context of significant changes in socio-cultural life, there is a general tendency to change stereotypes of men (boys) and women (girls), which means that the goal is to recognize a person's individuality, self-awareness regardless of gender, the ability to freely and fully express their thoughts, whether they are a boy or a girl, the ability to make decisions, self-confidence, and the ability to control their emotions and verbal and non-verbal behavior.

When raising and educating children, teachers should take into account their gender characteristics. Boys and girls differ not only in appearance: male and female natures bloom long before puberty, at the age of 5-7, and manifested from the moment they enter primary school, leaving a clear mark on their feelings, consciousness and behavior.

It is important for teachers to develop gender sensitivity, which means the ability to perceive, recognize and model the influence of verbal and nonverbal communication and other social or environmental circumstances on the formation of a child's gender identity.

At this point, it is worth giving some concepts related to the topic. There are various definitions of the concept of "gender". To summarize them, we can say that gender is a set of social and cultural norms that society requires people to fulfill based on their biological sex. Being a man or a woman in society means not only having certain anatomical characteristics, but also fulfilling defined gender roles.

Teachers should never forget that we have before us not only a child, but also a boy or a girl with their own upbringing, thinking, feelings. They need to be raised, taught and even loved in the right ways. Of course, children need to be loved. It is important never to compare and separate boys and girls.

Gender characteristics have been studied for a long time by psychologists and teachers T. V. Bendas, V. D. Eremeeva, T. P. Khrizman, S. Bern, I. S. Kon, A. A. Loginova, D. V. Kolesova and others. Because all children develop differently.

V.D. Eremeeva and T.P. Khrizman in their research concluded that by the age of one, the differences in the mental development of boys and girls reach such a high level that they are manifested in their behavior. So, their mental functions are formed differently, all areas are developed differently. So, girls are born 3-4 weeks older,

and before they enter primary school, girls can lag behind boys by up to a year. This affects the formation of gender characteristics in children. In the intellectual sphere, boys have lower indicators than girls in perceiving space, colors, and distinguishing their shades. This is due to the fact that men's vision is more adapted to distance, that is, "tunnel". The production of testosterone (male hormone) affects the perception of the color palette, so men perceive colors less. But boys are superior in the perception of time. Therefore, they can more successfully plan the organization of their activities than girls. They perceive objects as a whole. Boys pay less attention to details, they see the whole picture. But their thought processes are faster. Therefore, their mathematical abilities are also higher.

They always look for logic in everything, but at the same time they think outside the box. It is important for them not to complete tasks according to an algorithm, but to find their own way to solve them, which seems more logical to them.

Boys' speech is less active. Oratory skills are formed in the process of education and upbringing. They are more able to convey the sequence of events using action verbs. When performing tasks, attention is paid to the accuracy of the work. Accelerating the pace of work leads to a decrease in accuracy. Observation is higher, memory retention is worse. They rely on understanding events and processes, not memory. The speed of memorization is slower and the duration of memorization is longer.

Girls are superior in perceiving space, colors and distinguishing their shades.

They have the most developed peripheral vision, and the viewing angle is on average 90 degrees. The difference in color perception is due to the presence of more cells responsible for color perception. They have a lower indicator of time perception

than boys. They overestimate time intervals and therefore seem slower. Perception is more detailed. Girls often pick up details better, even the smallest ones, or even perceive them first, and then the whole object. Therefore, they prefer to analyze rather than generalize.

Algorithmic, concrete thinking: This means that it is easier for girls to act according to a plan or algorithm, and they rarely and unwillingly deviate from it. They are less prone to spatial thinking. They solve speech problems better. They are prone to subject-evaluative speech, use nouns, adjectives, addresses, statements. They prefer to answer with memorized phrases to make speech more coherent and coherent.

They use their own words less. The answer is characterized by a large number of details. Girls retain what they have learned in their memory for a long time. It is easier for them to remember than to understand. And therefore the speed of memorization is higher and the duration of memorization is shorter than that of boys.

Girls studying in primary school usually develop speech better, they are often physically stronger than boys and have a higher biological age. They overcome boys not physically, but through verbal communication. Primary school students ask three times more questions and enrich their speech with the additions "Isn't it true?", "Isn't it so?" But almost all healthy girls of primary school age have the same range of thinking and answers. Usually, since boys often have a delay in speech activity, there is more opportunity for individuality among them, they think externally and interestingly, but their inner world is often hidden from us, because they are less likely to express it in words. Therefore, girls play games based on dialogue, such as games that reflect the family, and so on, which are more verbal. Boys, on the other

hand, use movement, physical, etc. games that use less communication. And if they play together with girls, it seems to girls that boys are silent, that they do not think, do not look for solutions. In the emotional-volitional sphere, boys are more rational and less impulsive. Boys are also emotionally sensitive, but they control their emotions better and hide or even deny problems with emotions. They are calmer in response to praise and accusations.

In the emotional-volitional sphere, boys are more rational and less impulsive. Boys are also emotionally sensitive, but they control their emotions better and hide or even deny problems with emotions. They are calmer in response to praise and accusations. It is more difficult to touch them, make them laugh or cry. They strive to be more independent from their parents and become independent in behavior. Boys are more aggressive. They often experience anger and sometimes express these emotions without feeling it. Boys are more prone to stress in learning. Tests at school, constant reprimands from parents and teachers for poor performance, meeting new people - all this affects their stress.

Girls are more emotional. In general, they can be described as "emotionally impressionable." Girls are somewhat empathetic, better interpret emotions and are more adept at expressing emotions nonverbally. Violation of the norms accepted in their social group is painfully experienced. They prefer not to break the rules, but do not tolerate others breaking them. It is difficult for them to worry about failures and are easily offended for no reason. More proud and impressionable. And therefore they react more sharply to the tone of the remark than to the content of this remark. They do not like to joke, but their reaction is often demonstratively impressive to those around them. They constantly need emotional support. Sometimes even an

approving look is enough for girls to feel this support. They transfer the assessment of effectiveness to personal relationships.

In the motivational sphere, boys react negatively when the content and forms of educational activities do not correspond to their individual characteristics, they select knowledge, receive conflicting assessments and study less successfully.

Girls, if the content and forms of educational activities do not correspond to their individual characteristics, are more loyal to them, learn more easily, stably, suggestibly, disciplined and successfully.

In the communicative sphere, boys do not want to take care of anyone. It is more important for them to act than to communicate. They are not particularly sensitive to violations committed by themselves or other children. And therefore they often break the rules in companies, which brings boys closer together. But at the same time they often argue about things that do not exist. They are less inclined to turn to adults and complain less. Most often they want to communicate with their fathers and ask for help from their mothers.

Girls are prone to caring activities. They like to feed, care for, worry and take care of others. They often criticize, instruct and teach others. They are less likely to take the initiative in communicating with their peers; It is more difficult for them to function in new conditions without the help of adults. They need guidance and encouragement or praise. Girls are more sensitive to interpersonal relationships. They often argue among themselves. In conflicts and disputes, they rely on adults and therefore often turn to adults with requests and complaints. Girls, of course, have better fluency of speech, reading speed and spelling. However, finding word combinations and solving crossword puzzles is better demonstrated by boys and

young men. This once again confirms the male gender's tendency to search for new non-standard solutions and innovations.

T.V. Bendas analyzed various studies on gender and sex-related communication. He concluded that girls are better at distinguishing sounds at the beginning of primary school. Boys are better at identifying nonverbal sounds, for example, the sounds made by various animals. This probably indicates that they are more focused on the objective world, rather than the social one. In addition, girls are more prone to anxiety, attach greater importance to emotions and interpersonal relationships, are sensitive to criticism from close people, are more often depressed, and show positive emotions very clearly. They do not hesitate to show emotional reactions to others and determine the feelings of others with great accuracy. At school, girls are more interested in classes and work than boys, but teachers either consider boys and girls to be the same or pay more attention to boys than girls.

Boys tend to hide their emotions, especially negative ones, they are emotionally reserved and do not tend to show their feelings even with family and friends; However, in some cases, boys are emotionally superior to girls: this applies to emotions such as anger, hatred and disgust, as well as to the correct decoding of signals indicating that the people around them are experiencing the same emotions.

The American scientist J. Kramer studied the specifics of gender perception. He concluded that the perception of girls and boys is different: girls pay attention to the details of the perceived object, while boys pay attention to the object as a whole. However, if girls are given the task of paying attention to general features, they do it just as successfully as boys. Thus, the differences in perception between boys and girls lie in the different ways of perceiving.

The data of the German researcher J. Gluck are extremely interesting. He concluded that girls and women can be at the same level of success as men in solving spatial problems, but they prefer to choose a different solution strategy. This clearly shows us that both sexes can achieve the same success, but at the same time demonstrate their own uniqueness in methods. And if girls are taught the same methods that boys use, they will show the same results. Thus, when forming the communicative abilities and gender cultural characteristics of younger schoolchildren, teachers and parents should take into account their gender characteristics. Girls and boys differ not only physiologically, but also gender differences between boys and girls are already evident in the first months of their life. For example, girls develop physically and psychologically a little faster than boys. Girls and boys should be educated taking into account their natural and social characteristics -. It is necessary to know gender characteristics in order to take this into account during training, in the process of communicative interaction, when creating criteria for assessing success, when forming a team, etc. Gender differences between boys and girls can be observed in the intellectual, emotional-volitional, motivational and communicative spheres. Boys and girls differ in all mental functions. And, of course, when teaching and educating students in primary grades, it is necessary to take into account all these differences, to use various methods and tools that are most appropriate for the formation of gender culture. Using the teacher's knowledge of the differences in the developmental characteristics of girls and boys helps to more successfully master knowledge and the curriculum. The ability to apply knowledge about gender differences in primary school students in practice should encourage teachers to approximately equalize children without

resorting to double standards. Taking into account the gender characteristics of subjects ensures equal success for both sexes.

L

іКоломийченко, Л.В. Блочно-тематический план реализации программы волового воспитания детей дошкольного возраста [Текст] / Л. В. Коломийченко // Детский сад от А до Я. - 2006. - № 1. - С. 90 - 107.

о 2. Коломийченко, Л.В. Динамика и особенности полоролевой фсоциализации мальчиков и девочек дошкольного возраста [Текст] / Л. В. Коломийченко, О. В. Прозументик // Детский сад от А до Я. - 2006. - № 1. - С. s

е 3. Перлова, Ю.В. Преемственность гендерного воспитания детей дстаршего дошкольного и младшего школьного возраста. Канд. дис, Екатеринбург, 2014 г.

4. Фадеев, С.Б. Народная культура как средство формирования гендерной толерантности у детей старшего дошкольного возраста [Текст]: автореф. дис. канд. пед. наук / С. Б. Фадеев. - Екатеринбург, 2012.

5. Аскарова Г.Б., Курбатова Ю.В. Формирование гендерной компетентности детей младшего школьного возраста // Балтийский гуманитарный журнал. 2016. Т. 5. № 2 (15). С. 169-172.

6. Гахраманова Г.Н. Исследование социальных механизмов формирования гендерных различий // XXI век: итоги прошлого и проблемы настоящего плюс. 2015. Т. 2. № 1 (23). С. 56-62.

7. Степанова Н.В., Петрова В.Н. Влияние гендерных установок в ситуации конфликта на поведение в межличностных конфликтах юношей и

девушек // Вектор науки Тольяттинского государственного университета.
Серия: Педагогика, психология. 2012.№ 3. С. 207-209.